

IMPLOSION OF COMPOSITE SHELLS UNDER BLAST

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SUMMARY

Analytical and finite element solutions are presented in this paper for the impulsive response of laminated composite cylindrical shells subjected to uniform and asymmetric pressure pulse loading (side-on explosion). Unstable buckling modes arise depending on shell geometry, material properties and load intensity.

Keywords: blast, composite shell, dynamic pulse buckling.

INTRODUCTION

Laminated composite cylindrical shells are finding widespread applications in aerospace, transportation and marine industries. In some of these applications, the strength and stability of the composite cylindrical shell may be compromised external pressure pulse loading, such as one caused by a nearby explosion. There are numerous solutions for the collapse and failure of isotropic, cylindrical shells subjected to external blast loading, but only a few papers can be found concerning that of the laminated cylindrical shells in recent years [1-3]. Many of these solutions describe the shell response under periodic loading (vibration) or when the pressure pulse is applied while the shell is deforming. This paper examines dynamic pulse buckling of a laminated composite shell subjected to impulsive pressure loads. It follows from the principles governing pulse buckling of metallic shells in Ref. [4].

PROBLEM FORMULATION

Consider a long and thin, laminated composite cylinder of radius a and thickness h , and subjected to impulsive pressure loading as shown in Figs. 1(a)-(c). The composite shell may be subjected to uniformly-distributed impulsive pressure loads

$$p(t) = p_o \left[1 - \frac{t}{\Delta T} \right] \quad (1)$$

or non-axisymmetric impulsive pressure loads, such as one caused by a side-on explosions

$$p(\theta, t) = \begin{cases} p_o \cos^2 \theta \left[1 - \frac{t}{\Delta T} \right], & |\theta| \leq \pi/2 \\ 0, & |\theta| > \pi/2 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where p_o is the peak pressure, ΔT is the pulse duration, and t is time.

Figure 1 Composite cylinder under external pressure pulse loading: (a) Shell geometry, (b) Uniform over-pressure, and (c) Side-on explosion.

We limit our discussion to shells that are thin, $a/h > 10$, and long, $L/a > 20$, where L is the length of the shell. The later assumption combined with the fact that the pressure load do not vary along the shell longitudinal axis allows us to consider the cylinder as a ring deforming under plane strain conditions. Following the plane strain assumptions, $\varepsilon_x = 0$, $\varepsilon_{x\theta} = 0$, $\kappa_x = 0$, and $\kappa_{x\theta} = 0$. The hoop strain ε_θ in the shell is

$$\varepsilon_\theta = \varepsilon_{\theta m} + z\kappa_\theta \quad (3)$$

where $\varepsilon_{\theta m}$ is the mid-surface strain, κ_θ is the change in curvature of the shell and z the radial coordinate in shell measured from the mid surface of the shell. As shown in

Fig. 1 (a), the cylindrical shell has radial displacement $w(\theta, t)$ and angular displacement $v(\theta, t)$. Points on the mid-surface of the cylindrical shell have polar coordinates a, θ before deformation and r, ϕ after deformation. The radial displacement is given by

$$w = a - r \quad (4)$$

and the angular displacement is given by

$$\frac{v}{a} = \phi - \theta \quad (5)$$

The mid-surface strain is

$$\varepsilon_{\theta n} = \frac{1}{a} \left[\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial \theta} \right)^2 + (a-w)^2 \left(1 + \left(\frac{1}{a} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \theta} \right)^2 \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1 \quad (6)$$

The change in shell curvature is

$$\kappa_{\theta} = \frac{1}{a^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \theta^2} + w \right) \quad (7)$$

EQUATIONS OF MOTION

It is convenient to derive the equations of motion for the shell using the Lagrangian method. In this method, the Lagrangian is $L = T - \Pi$, where T is the kinetic energy and Π is the total potential energy of the shell. The kinetic energy of the shell is given by

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \rho h \int_0^{2\pi} \left[\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right] a d\theta \quad (8)$$

In general, the total potential energy of the shell is the sum of the strain energy U and potential of the applied loads. For an impulsively-loaded shell, the total potential energy of the shell consists only of strain energy because energy is transferred from the pressure pulse as an initial velocity or impulse. There are no loads acting on the shell during deformation and $\Pi = U$.

Strain Energy of a Laminated Composite Shell

Following plane strain assumptions, the elastic strain energy of a long, composite shell is

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int (A_{22} \varepsilon_{\theta n}^2 + B_{12} \varepsilon_{\theta n} \kappa_{\theta} + B_{22} \varepsilon_{\theta n} \kappa_{\theta} + D_{22} \kappa_{\theta}^2) a d\theta \quad (9)$$

where $A_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k - z_{k-1})$ is the membrane stiffness, $B_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2)$

is the coupling stiffness, $D_{ij} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^n (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3)$ is the bending stiffness, \bar{Q}_{ij} is the

reduced stiffness matrix, and n is the total number of plies. We examine a special class of laminated composite shells that are orthotropic, mid-surface symmetric and quasi-isotropic. In shells that are orthotropic and mid-surface symmetric, $B_{ij} = 0$. For quasi-isotropic shells, $B_{12} = 0$ and $B_{22} = 0$. In these types of laminated composite shells, the elastic strain energy reduces to

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int (A_{22} \varepsilon_{\theta n}^2 + D_{22} \kappa_{\theta}^2) a d\theta \quad (10)$$

Initial Velocity

The initial velocity imparted to the shell from the impulsive pressure is found from conservation of momentum

$$\rho h \frac{dw}{dt}(\theta, 0) = \int_0^{\Delta T} p(\theta, t) dt \quad (11)$$

Substituting the pressure pulse defined in Eqs. (1) and (2) into Eq. (11) gives

$$\frac{dw}{dt}(\theta, 0) = v_o \quad (12)$$

for the uniformly distributed load and

$$\frac{dw}{dt}(\theta, 0) = v_o \cos^2 \theta \quad (13)$$

for the side-on pressure pulse, where $v_o = \frac{p_o \Delta T}{2 \rho h}$ is the amplitude of the distributed velocity field.

Normalized Variables

Define a normalized radial deflection $\zeta = \frac{w}{a}$, tangential deflection, $\psi = \frac{v}{a}$, and

time $\tau = \frac{ct}{a}$, where $c = \sqrt{\frac{A_{22}}{\rho h}}$ is the wave speed in the circumferential direction.

The kinetic and potential energy in terms of the above normalized variables are

$$T = \frac{1}{2} A_{22} a \int_0^{2\pi} (\dot{\zeta}^2 + \dot{\psi}^2) d\theta \quad (14)$$

where $\dot{[]} = \partial [] / \partial \tau$ and

$$U = \frac{1}{2} A_{22} a \int_0^{2\pi} [(\psi' - \zeta)^2 + (\psi' - \zeta)(\zeta'^2 - 2\zeta\psi') + \alpha^2(\zeta'' + \zeta)^2] d\theta \quad (15)$$

where $\alpha^2 = D_{22} / (a^2 A_{22})$ and $[]' = \partial [] / \partial \theta$.

The normalized initial velocity are

$$\dot{\zeta}(\theta, 0) = \frac{v_o}{c} \quad (16)$$

for the uniformly loaded shell and

$$\dot{\zeta}(\theta,0) = \frac{v_o}{c} \text{Cos}^2 \theta \quad (17)$$

for the shell with side-on pressure loading.

FOURIER SERIES SOLUTION

Assume a Fourier series representation of the normalized radial and tangential displacement

$$\zeta = a_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [a_n \text{Cos}(n\theta) + b_n \text{Sin}(n\theta)] \quad (18)$$

and

$$\psi = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [c_n \text{Cos}(n\theta) + d_n \text{Sin}(n\theta)] \quad (19)$$

Following the inextensionality condition [5,6], $\psi' = \zeta - a_0$ and one gets that $c_n = -b_n/n$ and $d_n = a_n/n$. Substituting Eqs. (18) and (19) into Eqs. (14) and (15) and using inextensionality condition give

$$T = \pi A_{22} a \left[\dot{a}_0^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{n^2 + 1}{n^2} \right) (\dot{a}_n^2 + \dot{b}_n^2) \right] \quad (20)$$

for the kinetic energy

$$U = \pi A_{22} a \left\{ a_0^2 (1 + \alpha^2) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[a_0 (2 - n^2) + \alpha^2 (n^2 - 1)^2 \right] (a_n^2 + b_n^2) \right\} \quad (21)$$

for the strain energy. Since we will limit our analysis to small deflections, terms of order higher than a_n^2 and b_n^2 have been neglected. Lagrange's equations of motion for the shell is given by

$$\frac{d}{d\tau} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{a}_i} \right) + \frac{\partial U}{\partial a_i} = 0 \quad (22)$$

Substituting Eqs. (20) and (21) into Eq. (22) gives the solution for the breathing mode ($n = 0$)

$$\ddot{a}_0 + a_0 (1 + \alpha^2) - \frac{1}{4} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (n^2 - 2) (a_n^2 + b_n^2) = 0 \quad (23)$$

and for modes of $n \geq 1$

$$\ddot{a}_n + \frac{n^2}{n^2 + 1} \left[(n^2 - 1)^2 \alpha^2 - (n^2 - 2) a_0 \right] a_n = 0, \quad (24)$$

and

$$\ddot{b}_n + \frac{n^2}{n^2 + 1} \left[(n^2 - 1)^2 \alpha^2 - (n^2 - 2) a_0 \right] b_n = 0, \quad (25)$$

The breathing mode is in general coupled with the bending modes. The above equations of motion are solved from initial conditions: $\zeta(\theta, 0) = 0$ and

$$\dot{\zeta}(\theta, 0) = \dot{a}_{00} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [\dot{a}_{n0} \cos(n\theta) + \dot{b}_{n0} \sin(n\theta)] \quad (26)$$

where $\dot{a}_0(0) = \dot{a}_{00}$, $\dot{a}_n(0) = \dot{a}_{n0}$, $\dot{b}_n(0) = \dot{b}_{n0}$, $a_n(0) = 0$, and $b_n(0) = 0$. When deflections are small, a_n^2 and b_n^2 are negligible compared to a_n and b_n . Equations (23)-(25) reduce to

$$\ddot{a}_0 + a_0(1 + \alpha^2) = 0 \quad (27)$$

$$\ddot{a}_n + (\Omega_n - \mu_n \sin \tau) a_n = 0, \quad n \geq 1 \quad (28)$$

$$\ddot{b}_n + (\Omega_n - \mu_n \sin \tau) b_n = 0, \quad n \geq 1 \quad (29)$$

where $\Omega_n = \frac{\alpha^2 n^2 (n^2 - 1)^2}{(n^2 + 1)}$ and $\mu_n = \frac{n^2 (n^2 - 2)}{(n^2 + 1) \sqrt{1 + \alpha^2}} \dot{a}_{00}$. The differential equations

described in Eqs. (28) and (29) are Mathieu's equation [7]. They yield unstable solutions for values of μ_n and Ω_n that are not in the cross-hatched zones shown in

Fig. 2 (a). We examine specific solutions for the uniform and side-on pressure loads.

Figure 2 Mathieu's stability diagrams: (a) expanded and (b) reduced scales.

Uniform Over-Pressure

Under uniform pressure load, there can be no rigid body motion of the shell. Hence, the terms involving $n = 1$ do not exist and the solution for the shell is given in terms of its Fourier series

$$\zeta = a_0 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [a_n \text{Cos}(n\theta) + b_n \text{Sin}(n\theta)] \quad (30)$$

The initial velocity condition becomes

$$\dot{\zeta}(\theta,0) = \dot{a}_{00} + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [\dot{a}_{n0} \text{Cos}(n\theta) + \dot{b}_{n0} \text{Sin}(n\theta)] \quad (31)$$

For the uniform velocity, $\dot{a}_{00} = \frac{v_o}{c}$, $\dot{a}_{n0} = 0$ and $\dot{b}_{n0} = 0$. Thus, the solution for

Eq. (27) is

$$a_0(\tau) = \frac{v_o}{c} \sin \tau \quad (32)$$

This is simply the breathing mode. The stability of laminated composite cylindrical shells follows exactly the same trends as for an isotropic, elastic shell under uniformly distributed impulsive pressure as discussed in Refs. [4] and [6], and will not be repeated here.

Side-On Explosion

For the side-on pressure pulse described by Eq. (2), the shell deforms and moves with rigid-body motion ($n = 1$ term is not neglected) and only the Cosine terms of the Fourier series are retained because of load symmetry, i.e., $b_n = 0$. The normalized solution becomes

$$\zeta = a_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \text{Cos}(n\theta) \quad (33)$$

The centroid of the shell will have a non-zero velocity in a fixed plane, and we will refer to motion in a plane travelling with it. The initial velocity of the shell is then written as

$$\dot{\zeta}(\theta,0) = \dot{a}_{00} + \frac{1}{2} \dot{a}_{10} \text{Cos}(\theta) + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \dot{a}_{n0} \text{Cos}(n\theta) \quad (34)$$

where $\dot{a}_{00} = \frac{1}{4} \frac{v_o}{c}$ and

$$\dot{a}_{n0} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left\{ \frac{2}{n} \text{Sin}\left(\frac{n\pi}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{(n+2)} \text{Sin}\left(\frac{\pi(n+2)}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{(n-2)} \text{Sin}\left(\frac{\pi(n-2)}{2}\right) \right\} \frac{v_o}{c}, \quad n \geq 1$$

Once again the stability of the solution depends on the values of μ_n and Ω_n . If these lie in the stable regions of Mathieu's diagram, the shell undergoes deformation with each mode shape. We examine stable shell deformations and the stability of the composite shell when it is subjected to a side-on explosion in the next sections.

SHELL DEFORMATIONS

Three laminated shell geometries are chosen: an orthotropic shell made of woven roving E-Glass/Vinyl Ester, and a mid-surface symmetric, laminated shell ($[60^0/-45^0]_s$) and a quasi-isotropic, laminated shell ($60^0/0^0/-60^0$) made of unidirectional E-Glass/Epoxy plies. Each of the cylinders has a total shell thickness of $h = 4$ mm and a shell radius of $a = 80$ mm. The impulse is chosen so that μ_n and Ω_n occur in the stable region of Mathieu's diagram. These points are plotted on a reduced scale of the Mathieu's diagram in Fig. 2 (b). Figures 3 and 4 (a) and (b) show the transient deflections of the shells as well as finite element analysis predictions using ABAQUS Explicit. There is very good agreement between analytical and FEA results.

Figure 3 Transient deflections of the orthotropic, woven roving E-Glass/Vinyl Ester shell; $p_o = 10$ MPa, $\Delta T = 3.5 \mu s$.

Figure 4 Transient deflections of the E-Glass/Epoxy shells; $p_o = 10$ MPa, $\Delta T = 2.9 \mu s$: (a) mid-surface symmetric ($[60^0/-45^0]_s$) and (b) quasi-isotropic ($60^0/0^0/-60^0$).

SHELL INSTABILITY

Instability may occur at higher impulse loads or initial shell velocities. Figure 5(a) shows the values of μ_n and Ω_n plotted on Mathieu's stability graph for various normalized velocity v_o/c in the woven E-Glass/Vinyl Ester, orthotropic shell. Points on the Mathieu's stability diagram shift upwards as the normalized velocity v_o/c increases. The fifth and seventh mode both just becomes unstable when $v_o/c = 0.0448$ and the critical impulse for buckling instability for this shell is 882 Pa-s ($p_o = 504 \text{ MPa}$, $\Delta T = 3.5 \mu\text{s}$). The Mathieu's stability diagram is also used to determine the stability of the mid-surface symmetric and quasi-isotropic E-Glass/Epoxy shells in Fig. 5(b). The buckling pressures and the unstable modes are listed in Table 1.

Figure 5 Mathieu's stability diagrams: (a) effect of increasing v_o/c in orthotropic, E-Glass/Vinyl Ester shell and (b) critical buckling modes for three laminates.

Table 1 Critical buckling pressure for composite shells.

	$c(m/s)$	α^2	$(p_o)_{crit}$ (MPa)	$\Delta t(\mu\text{s})$	Unstable Modes
Orthotropic E-Glass/Vinyl Ester	3,525	$2.08e^{-4}$	504	3.5	5,7
Mid-surface symmetric E-Glass/Epoxy ($[60^0/-45^0]_s$)	3,723	$2.39e^{-4}$	860	2.9	5
Quasi-isotropic E-Glass/Epoxy ($60^0/0^0/-60^0$)	4,321	$1.82e^{-4}$	752	2.9	7,9

The critical buckling pressures depend on the circumferential wave speed $c = \sqrt{\frac{A_{22}}{\rho h}}$ and bending to extension ratio $\alpha^2 = D_{22} / (a^2 A_{22})$, which are listed for each shell in Table 1. In general, the critical buckling pressure increases with increasing values of α^2 . For the orthotropic, woven roving E-Glass/Vinyl Ester shell, $\alpha^2 = h^2 / (12a^2)$ and a shell made of this material becomes thicker with increasing values of α^2 . For the laminated E-Glass/Epoxy shell, α^2 is controlled not only by shell thickness but also by the layup.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Analytical solutions for the transient response of orthotropic, mid-surface symmetric and quasi-isotropic, laminated composite shell subjected to uniform and asymmetric pressure pulse loading (side-on explosion) have been presented. The equations of motion governing shell deformations are of a type belonging to Mathieu's differential equations, which sometimes yield unstable results. Unstable buckling modes arise depending on shell geometry, material properties and load intensity. The stable transient deformations of an orthotropic E-Glass/Vinyl Ester shell and a mid-surface symmetric and a quasi-isotropic E-Glass/Epoxy shell with a side-on explosion compared very well with finite element predictions using ABAQUS Explicit.

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